

REPRODUCIBLE BASELINING AND BENCHMARKING OF NETWORK PERFORMANCE WITH PERFSONAR

*WORK PACKAGE 4: BIG-DATA ELECTRON AND
CORRELATIVE MICROSCOPY FROM
INSTRUMENT TO PUBLICATION*

Chris MYERS

David POGER

AUSTRALIAN CHARACTERISATION COMMONS AT SCALE

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Chris MYERS

AARNet Pty Ltd

Dr David POGER

Microscopy Australia

Contact:

Chris Myers

chris.myers@aarnet.edu.au

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Executive summary

Researchers and research facilities transfer large volumes of data routinely within and between institutions and across countries and the globe. Monitoring and predicting the performance of a network as well as identifying anomalies when they arise is therefore critical. In the present report, the toolkit perfSONAR is described. perfSONAR is used by research and education organisations across the world to measure a range of network properties. Advantages of perfSONAR are briefly presented alongside recommendations on how information technology and e-research specialists, facilities and researchers may exploit and interpret information from perfSONAR. This work was undertaken under Work Package 4: “Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication” of the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project.

1 Introduction

Many fields of modern scientific research depend upon the frequent transfer of data across institutions and the world via computer networks. Ensuring that networks behave and perform as required is thus essential. Network performance is a composite property consisting of a range of qualitative and quantitative properties that collectively characterise the state or behaviour of the service supported by a network at a given discrete point in time or over a given period of time. Network performance reflects the end user's experience of the service.

Network performance-monitoring tools are generally broken down into two main categories: passive network-monitoring tools and active network-monitoring tools. Passive network-monitoring tools measure and record network traffic and uptime and provide a snapshot of the status of a service at a given point in time only (for example, whether a service is available or not). Such tools measure network performance using network usage at a given time without creating or modifying the traffic on the network. When data are transferred over a network from a source to a destination, they travel through a sequence of nodes called path. Passive network-monitoring tools do not provide a real understanding of the state of the nodes and the ability of a path to deliver performant data transit. In contrast, active network-monitoring tools measure and analyse network performance by timing probes as they travel through the network, that is specific volumes of test data called packets injected into a network at known locations and times. As a result, anomalies and issues in network behaviour and bottlenecks in network traffic can be located and identified.

Network baselining is monitoring and measuring the performance of a network over time. As the provider of Australia's national academic and research network, baselining network performance as well as detecting and diagnosing anomalies as they happen is at the core of AARNet's mission. Benchmarking a network is comparing its performance with respect to that of another network, an industry standard or any other external reference. Benchmarking tests whether a network behaves normally (that is within a range of acceptable parameter values) or as expected. Network baselining together with benchmarking allow for determining the reliability and predictability of the performance of a network, and can thus be used by AARNet, information technology and e-research specialists at universities, and research facilities and researchers to set expectations regarding the capacity for a network to transfer data. Importantly, network baselining is an iterative process: when a component of a network—hardware, software, software version in any part of the network from end to end—changes, it is necessary to repeat network performance baselining and compare the new baseline with the previous one to ensure that the quality of the service supported by the network is maintained or enhanced.

Identifying problems and recording when they arise in an environment that crosses institutional, facility and network infrastructure boundaries is a challenge. The schematic in Figure 1 shows that computer networks at universities and nationally are complex, multi-component systems sometimes consisting of subnetworks. For example, a network at a university campus may comprise subnetworks that vary in technical specifications such as the types of cables used (for example, fibre-optic cables and copper cables). From the initial point of capture from an instrument, data can be moved to various locations for various purposes

Figure 1 Schematic representation of a typical multi-component network composed of interlinked institutional or local network or subnetwork (for example, facility and laboratory networks).

such as processing, analysis, storage and archiving. Faults, instabilities and discrepancies in the behaviour of interconnected networks can therefore have multiple potential sources. This is all the more difficult in situations where some parties using AARNet's network do not have access to direct network-monitoring equipment such as with Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP) or access to streaming telemetry.

A previous review on data movement at electron microscopy facilities at Australian universities noted that a clear end-to-end understanding of network infrastructure was necessary to benefit fully from the infrastructure as well as identify and solve network-related issues.[1] It was recommended that, as a best practice, an initial baselining of network performance be conducted and then followed by additional baselining whenever an infrastructure component changed. In this context, AARNet examined several active network measurement and performance-monitoring systems using a range of key criteria. Specifically, the ability to observe, record, understand and predict network performance between network connection points such as instruments, data storage facilities and compute facilities along network paths within the same institution or between different institutions, was investigated. An active measurement solution was the preferred option as probes could be placed as close as possible to network equipment at partner organisations and at various points along network paths. The systems explored were also required to keep the same level of performance and functionalities as networks expanded with minimal changes to existing probes and, when available, with the integration of existing network of probes. Finally, cost and support for those systems were carefully examined. This criterion was especially important given that network metrics and network performance monitoring have not usually been a key consideration for universities, or even a service delivered by their information technology services. For those who have provided such service, it has not generally extended beyond campus boundaries.

After reviewing several product offerings, the network measurement toolkit perfSONAR¹ was found to meet most of the key criteria and be the best fit for AARNet and its partners (universities) but also for researchers and facilities such as microscopy facilities that rely heavily upon predictable performance of networks within and between institutions for their activities. Alternatives to perfSONAR include free programs such as RIPE Atlas² and commercial solutions such as SolarWinds[®].³

In this report, the network performance-monitoring system perfSONAR is described. The advantages of perfSONAR and the tools that it offers to monitor network behaviour are presented briefly. Examples of network metrics measured by perfSONAR and how perfSONAR outputs test results graphically are provided to illustrate how information technology and e-research specialists as well as facilities and researchers can utilise and interpret information from perfSONAR.

This work was undertaken under the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project, in particular under Work Package 4: “Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication”. This report is intended as the conclusion of the work planned for deliverable WP4.3: “Develop reproducible baselining or benchmarking of file-transfer performance”.

2 Description of perfSONAR

perfSONAR (performance Service-Oriented Network monitoring Architecture)¹ is an open-source, modular toolkit for active network performance monitoring dedicated to research and education.[2] The development of perfSONAR is the fruit of an ongoing international partnership initially founded in 2014 between the Energy Sciences Network ESnet (USA), the Pan-European Research and Education Network GÉANT, Indiana University (USA) and the National Research and Education Network Internet2 (USA), later joined by the University of Michigan (USA) and the Brazilian National Research and Education Network (Rede Nacional de Ensino e Pesquisa).

perfSONAR analyses and diagnoses network behaviours in near-real time across an entire end-to-end network path. perfSONAR aims to facilitate the collection and sharing of network performance information. Practically, perfSONAR measures the capacity and the quality of a network as well as the consistency of its behaviour over time for research facilities and researchers to transfer their data reliably and predictably.

The source code is freely available as a GitHub repository.⁴ The online documentation is comprehensive and provides instructions to instal the software on a range of operating systems (CentOS, Debian, Ubuntu) and the platform Docker.⁵ perfSONAR is provided free of cost under the Apache License.

¹ <https://www.perfsonar.net>

² <https://atlas.ripe.net>

³ <https://www.solarwinds.com>

⁴ <https://github.com/perfsonar>

⁵ http://docs.perfsonar.net/install_getting.html

The perfSONAR toolkit provides preconfigured security tools. In particular, it uses a default set of firewall rules that only allow connections to specific network ports by tools and services used by perfSONAR (Table 1). The protocols and ports listed in Table 1 are frequent sources of errors when they are improperly configured.

Table 1 List of tools and services available in the perfSONAR toolkit that require ports to be open for the transport protocols. *Source: https://www.perfsonar.net/deployment_security.html.*

Tool or service ^a	Port number	Transport protocol ^b
ICMP	—	—
iperf2	5001	TCP
iperf3	5201	TCP
Lookup service	8090	TCP
Management interfaces	80, 443	TCP
nuttcp	5000, 5101	TCP
NTP	123	TCP
OWAMP (control)	861	TCP
OWAMP (testing)	8760–9960	TCP, UDP
simplestreamer	5890–5900	TCP
traceroute	33434–33634	UDP
TWAMP (control)	862	TCP
TWAMP (testing)	18760-19960	TCP, UDP

^a ICMP, Internet Control Message Protocol; NTP, Network Time Protocol; OWAMP, One-Way Active Measurement Protocol; TWAMP, Two-Way Active Measurement Protocol.

^b TCP, Transmission Control Protocol; UDP, User Datagram Protocol.

3 The choice of perfSONAR to monitor network performance

perfSONAR presents a range of advantages that makes it suitable to deploy for AARNet but also for universities, facilities and researchers. Specifically, perfSONAR allows for:

- real-time analysis and testing of the network path from one computer to another—or more broadly between two network endpoints (a source and a destination)—by measuring throughput, loss and latency (these properties are defined later);
- recording of analysis and testing results over time;
- keeping records of the network path via the `traceroute` utility (a network diagnostic tool that displays possible paths between two network endpoints via the internet);
- graphical presentation of analysis and testing results between different time points

and over periods of time;

- modification of tests to meet the environments in which AARNet and the research and education sector operate and adapt to potential limited-bandwidth paths;
- scaling to extremely large numbers of probes; and
- monitoring paths that had many owners.

In addition, perfSONAR supports multiple operating systems and deployment methodologies. The hardware requirements to run perfSONAR on a network were also judged reasonable.

The only missing desirable outcome in AARNet's evaluation was the ability to visualise network activity using the network visualisation tool Weathermap.⁶ However, since it would have required direct access to the network infrastructure (*i.e.* switches) at universities, it was unlikely that this criterion would have been met.

4 Measuring network performance with perfSONAR

Network performance metrics are qualitative and quantitative ways to observe and understand the behaviour of a network, and to determine if the observed behaviour is desired or abnormal. For example, the network uptime which refers to the time when a network is up and running, is often taken as a measure of the availability of a service to its users. perfSONAR monitors network performance between two points in a network from the perspective of an end user rather than focusing on monitoring the activity of specific devices in a network.

4.1 Network properties measured by perfSONAR

The tools in perfSONAR measure a range of properties to baseline and benchmark performance of the whole network or specific paths, links or segments. Network links and segments are depicted in Figure 2. The properties characterised by perfSONAR include:

- **network capacity** (bandwidth): maximum amount of data that can cross a given link, segment or path (Figure 2);
- **network utilisation**: relative amount of the network capacity used at a given time;
- **throughput** (also called “achievable bandwidth”): maximum possible amount of data that is successfully transferred over a network at a given time. It is often measured for paths versus individual segments;
- **one-way latency**: the time for data to travel from one host to another;
- **round-trip time** (or two-way latency): the time for data to travel from one host to another and back to the first host;
- **jitter**: the variation in arrival times for packets between two endpoints;
- **packet loss**: the number of packets of data dropped for any reason on a network segment or path; and
- **packet duplication**: the number of packets duplicated for any reason on a network segment or path.

⁶ <https://www.network-weathermap.com>

Figure 2 Schematic representation of network nodes, links, segments and paths. Three paths connecting endpoints A and B are shown in blue, purple and green. The path in blue consists of two segments: segment A-1-2 (solid line) that connects endpoint A to node 2 in two links via node 1, and segment 2-3-4-B (dashed line) that connects node 2 to endpoint B in three links via nodes 3 and 4. Similarly, the path in purple is composed of two segments (solid line and dashed line) and the path in green, of three segments (solid line, dash line and dotted line).

Overall, the network performance properties measured by perfSONAR characterise four main categories of state or anomalies of a network:

- the theoretical capacity of a network to transfer data (measured by the network capacity);
- the actual capacity of a network to transfer data at a given time or over a given period of time (measured by network utilisation and throughput);
- issues causing slow data transfer over a network (measured by one-way latency, round-trip time and jitter); and
- issues causing loss or alteration of data during transfer (measured by packet loss and packet duplication).

Note, an issue or an anomaly occurs when the performance of a network deviates from its expected state.

Measuring network performance can help identify what can be achieved using a specific network or tailor a network to a specific usage. For example, bulk-data movement along a path requires high throughput that is underpinned by low (or zero) packet loss, stable jitter and low path utilisation.

4.2 The effect of performance-measuring tools on network behaviour

perfSONAR is a toolkit that consists of a range of utilities that have various purposes. Importantly, like any instrument or probe used in science and engineering, each tool has its advantages and drawbacks and may introduce artefacts and biases that need to be considered when interpreting measurements.

For example, loss of data (packet loss) during transfer can be measured in perfSONAR with

the tools `reno` and `htcp`. Packet loss can have a significant impact on the overall performance of a network and the ability to transfer data fast and reliably between two endpoints. Various factors are responsible for packet loss. A common cause is insufficient buffer memory at the destination endpoint which results in the inability to process data packets as they reach the destination endpoint. The destination endpoint then sends a signal to the source to reduce the rate at which packets are sent (throughput) and to send the missing packets again. Monitoring decrease in network throughput due to packet loss is thus important. Figure 3 shows an example of the effect of packet loss during data transfer through the measure of network throughput between endpoints (probes) located at increasing distances using the tools `reno` and `htcp`. The round-trip time between a source and a destination can be used as a proxy for the actual, physical distance between them because it is directly correlated with the distance separating two endpoints. For example, as indicated in Figure 3, a round-trip time of 10 ms corresponds to regional distances whereas a time of 70–100 ms is consistent with very large distances such as transcontinental, intercontinental and international distances. As can be seen, in the case of a lossless or virtually lossless transfer (on average, 1 packet lost out of 22000 packets sent, or 0.0046 % of the packets, in one direction), throughput decreases steadily and very slowly and remains high even at the longest distances (8.2 Gb/s at 90 ms

Figure 3 (a) Variation of the network throughput (in Gb/s, gigabit per second) with the round-trip time as measured by the tools `reno` and `htcp`, predicted for `reno` and for a path with virtually no data loss. (b) Zoom in the region of low throughput (lower than 1 Gb/s). Adapted from: <https://fasterdata.es.net/network-tuning/tcp-issues-explained/packet-loss>

round-trip time; Gb/s, gigabit per second). Note, the overall downward trend of throughput was expected because the probability of losing packets of data increases with the length of the transit of data. In contrast, when throughput was measured with `reno` and `htcp`, significant drops in packet loss were measured, leading to less than 1 Gb/s of throughput for round-trip times greater than 12 and 30 ms using `reno` and `htcp`, respectively. That throughput decreased illustrates that both tools changed the behaviour of the network in order to measure a property. It also shows that `reno` and `htcp` affected throughput differently as the initial drop in throughput was sharper when using `reno` than with `htcp` and the average throughput measured or predicted from theory with `reno` stayed lower than with `htcp` over long distances.

Figure 3 demonstrates that tools available in perfSONAR that can be used for similar purposes are indeed not equivalent and may impact network behaviour differently. Some utilities are better suited to specific conditions than other. Therefore, it is recommended to measure a range of properties to capture the instantaneous or time-averaged performance of a network rather than focusing on the measure of single property by a single tool.

4.3 A global network of perfSONAR nodes

The global network of perfSONAR nodes can be exploited to monitor and benchmark the performance of a network at an institution. A map of perfSONAR nodes is available online.⁷ Figure 4 shows a screenshot of the information available for every node (for example, location and IP address) alongside a map of perfSONAR nodes across the world.

The global map of perfSONAR nodes may be especially useful to facilities and researchers in two situations:

Figure 4 Screenshot of the information available for every node in the perfSONAR Lookup Service Directory. Inset, global map of perfSONAR nodes.

⁷ <http://stats.es.net/ServicesDirectory/>

- to test the performance of the network to a location where there is no existing or known perfSONAR node but where there is a known nearby node available; and
- to test and investigate issues in certain section of paths, in particular in the case of international connections or domestic networks outside the research and education sector.

5 Testing of perfSONAR

Two perfSONAR nodes were deployed within AARNet’s servers in the Data Transfer Node (DTN) test bed alongside two other test nodes located at Monash University and the University Wollongong. An existing node at the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) was also used. The five nodes were used to baseline the perfSONAR infrastructure. Table 2 lists the addresses (URLs, Uniform Resource Locators) of all five nodes used for testing perfSONAR. Tests were performed using a range of utilities to measure properties such as throughput, one-way latency, round-trip time and packet loss. Note, the purpose of the tests was primarily to explore the functionalities available in perfSONAR, the user experience and the ease of use for various audiences including information technology and e-research specialists at AARNet and universities, as well as researchers and staff at research facilities. The tests were not carried out to monitor, detect, diagnose or investigate anomalies.

Table 2 List of perfSONAR nodes used for testing.

URL ^a	Site
https://vic-crl2-ps1.ps.aarnet.net.au/toolkit	AARNet
https://vic-crl2-ps2.ps.aarnet.net.au/toolkit	AARNet
http://vm-118-138-254-213.erc.monash.edu.au/toolkit	Monash University
http://sonar.molecule.uow.edu.au/toolkit	University of Wollongong
http://perfsonar.nci.org.au	National Computational Infrastructure

^a URL, Uniform Resource Locator.

Figures 5 and 6 show screenshots of the perfSONAR graphical user interface. Figure 5 shows the main window upon loading. It contains a range of information on the utilities in use including their names (in this case, *esmond*, *lsregistration*, *owamp*, *pscheduler*, *psconfig* and *twamp*), their operational states (or statuses such as “running”), their versions, the network ports that they may be using and the URLs of the nodes that they may be using. Figure 6 shows how results performed at a given time are displayed. In panel a, network throughput, latency and packet loss between two servers (referred to as source and destination) were measured. The latency measured is the one-way latency or the round-trip time (two-way latency). All tests were run in the forward direction (movement of data from the source to the destination, represented schematically as a right arrow) and the reverse direction (movement of data from the destination to the source, indicated as a left arrow). The round-trip time was

SERVICE	STATUS	VERSION	PORTS
esmond - https://vic-cr12-ps2.ps.aarnet.net.au/esmond/perfsonar/archive/ https://localhost/esmond/perfsonar/archive/	Running	4.4.1-1.el7	
lsregistration	Running	4.4.1-1.el7	
owamp - Test ports: 8760-9960	Running	4.4.1-1.el7	861
pscheduler - https://vic-cr12-ps2.ps.aarnet.net.au/pscheduler https://localhost/pscheduler	Running	4.4.1-1.el7	
psconfig	Running	4.4.1-1.el7	
twamp - Test ports: 18760-19960	Running	4.4.1-1.el7	862

Figure 5 Screenshot of the main window in the perfSONAR graphical user interface. The areas labelled as 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 indicate: 1. the names of the utilities in use; 2. their current statuses; 3. the versions of the utilities; 4. the network ports used by each utility; and 5. the locations of the nodes used by each utility.

measured by moving data packets from the source to the destination and back to the source and was signalled by the addition of the note “(rtt)” next to the measurement. All the properties measured had comparable values in the forward and reverse directions or close to the expected values for round-trip measurements. This shows that no issue was detected during the tests. A notable anomaly is highlighted in red. Specifically, the round-trip time between the AARNet and NCI nodes was more than double the predicted time based on the one-way latency measured in the reverse direction (1.68 ms). The round-trip time was expected around 3.4 ms. Instead, it was measured at 7.52 ms. In this case, the delay did not stem from a network issue but was a known behaviour: the server located at NCI that hosts the perfSONAR node executes additional operations on incoming data. Those extra steps amounted to about 3.1 ms in apparent latency. In a general case, such an anomaly would require further investigation. The window displaying the tests also contains clickable links for additional information. For example, results of the tests using the `traceroute` utility are showed in panel b. `traceroute` identifies the path taken by data to transit from a source to a destination via various network nodes. Note, paths are called topologies in the output given by `traceroute`. The route taken from one node to another is called a hop and is represented schematically in panel c. Figure 6b shows the output of the `traceroute` analysis between perfSONAR nodes at AARNet and Monash University. The analysis was run several times. The nodes used by each hop are listed alongside the IP address of each node and the time taken by each hop (“delay”). By repeating the `traceroute` test, the network path can be checked for consistency over time. It allows for the detection and diagnosis of one-way and round-trip issues.

Figure 6 Screenshots of the perfSONAR graphical user interface. (a) Example of the display of the results from a series of tests (throughput, latency and packet loss). The latency measured is the one-way latency and the round-trip time (“rtt”). The red rectangle highlights a potential anomaly in the result of the round-trip time that could be investigated. (b) Example of results from the `traceroute` analysis. (c) Schematic representation of the paths tested in panel b.

A useful feature of perfSONAR is the ability to record and plot results from analysis over time. This allows for a retrospective analysis of network performance when issues or anomalies arise, and detect potential patterns or signs that may help diagnose and solve problems. Figure 7 shows a screenshot of the perfSONAR graphical user interface when network properties are examined over a set period of time. In this case, the variations of network throughput, packet loss and latency (one-way latency and round-trip time) between a node at AARNet (the source) and the node at Monash university (the destination) were plotted over a period of one month from 09.07.2022 to 09.08.2022. As for the measurements presented in Figure 6, Figure 7 shows measurements in both the forward and reverse direction (indicated as “fd” and “rd”, respectively). In the absence of any issue, network properties are expected to have the following behaviours over time:

- throughput: network throughput should converge and fluctuate around similar average values in both the forward and reverse directions;
- packet loss: data lost during transit should be close to zero on average in both the forward and reverse directions but discrete spikes of low magnitude can be expected due to inherent noise in the signal or other activities affecting traffic over the network;

and

- latency: the network one-way latency should converge and fluctuate around similar average values in both the forward and reverse directions, and the average round-trip time should be close to twice the average one-way latency.

Overall, the measurements in the forward and reverse directions in Figure 7 overlap well. This indicates that the network between the two nodes was stable over the period of time examined and, importantly, the behaviour of the network was predictable. Note, although a clear increase in the one-latency in the forward direction was observed for a few days, it returned to, and remained around, its average value afterwards. This demonstrates that network properties measured over time can be impacted by a range of factors that may introduce artefacts or degrade the network performance temporarily without necessarily revealing an issue in the network behaviour or performance. Such factors include: other tests being performed on the same perfSONAR node at the same time; intense traffic being carried on the network path examined; the presence of security devices along the network; and artefacts inherent in the tools used. In this case, that the round-trip time did not increase suggests that the utility used to measure the one-way latency might have been sensitive to one of those factors listed above, so the increase in the one-latency in the forward direction was likely to be artificial. In general, it is recommended measuring both the one-way latency and the round-trip time so artefacts can be easily identified. If the increase observed occurred several times over a longer time window, a further investigation into the cause(s) of the behaviour would be required.

Figure 7 Screenshot of perfSONAR test results measured between a source (1) and a destination (2) and over a given time period set by the user (3). The properties shown are throughput, packet loss and latency (one-way latency in brown, and round-trip time in orange). The properties were measured in both the forward direction (fd, solid lines) and reverse direction (rd, dotted lines).

6 Conclusion

The deployment and testing of perfSONAR at AARNet, Monash University and the University of Wollongong has demonstrated that perfSONAR contains a suite of tools that can be used by both information technology experts at AARNet and universities, and members of the research community (researchers and research facilities) to detect and diagnose issues or

anomalies in network performance. With perfSONAR, network performance can be monitored and analysed in real time, and measurements can be recorded over time for retrospective analysis. This makes perfSONAR very well suited to network baselining and benchmarking. It enables to predict the performance of a network and determine if a network has the capacity to meet users' expectations reliably for data transfer.

7 Contributorship

CM designed the work, deployed perfSONAR nodes at AARNet, Monash University and the University of Wollongong, and drafted the report. DP oversaw overall progress of the work and wrote the final report.

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